

THE IMPACT OF SILICON MASS ON THE RADIOLYSIS PROCESS OCCURRING UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF GAMMA- QUANTA ON NANO-Si/H₂O SUSPENSION SYSTEM

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In the thesis, the process of molecular hydrogen production via the radiolysis of water (H₂O) in a system composed of nano-sized SiO₂ particles ($d = 20$ nm) under the influence of γ -quanta (from a ⁶⁰Co source, $P = 9.276$ rad/s, $T = 300$ K) was investigated both experimentally and theoretically. The main objective of this study was to determine the radiation-chemical yield of molecular hydrogen by varying the mass of water in the nano-SiO₂/H₂O system.

Figure. Dependence of the radiation-chemical yield of molecular hydrogen, obtained from the radiolytic catalytic decomposition of water in nano-SiO₂/H₂O systems (with $m = 0.2$ g of SiO₂ nanoparticles, $d = 20$ nm), on the mass of water. The yield was calculated for the entire system (curve 1), for water (curve 2), and for nano-SiO₂ (curve 3), under the effect of γ -quanta (⁶⁰Co, $P = 9.276$ rad/s, $T = 300$ K).

It was observed that in systems where water is adsorbed onto the surface of nanoparticles, the radiation-chemical yield of molecular hydrogen was relatively low.

The thesis also presents specific dependencies of the radiation-chemical yield on the mass of water in the nano-SiO₂/H₂O system. It was determined that the maximum yield for the entire system was achieved at a water mass of 0.2 g, while at higher water masses, the yield gradually decreased. This behavior is attributed to the filling of the interparticle space with water, which reduces the effective emission of electrons from the solid phase into the liquid phase.